

PROMOTING SUSTAINABLE EMPLOYEE PERFORMANCE THROUGH GREEN HUMAN RESOURCES MANAGEMENT & GREEN BEHAVIOUR

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Abstract

Currently, the millennial generation is starting to dominate the work force which is expected to be a pioneer driving companies to implement more green behavior. This Study examines the influence Green Human Resources management, Green Commitment and Green behavior to Sustainable Employee Performance. SmartPLS 3 software was used to analyses the relationship form 150 valid responses. The finding of our study shows that Green Commitment can moderate the influence of Green behavior to Sustainable Employee Performance. Green Training and Green Compensation have an effect on Green Behavior while Green Recruitment and Green Performance Appraisal have no effect on Green Behavior. It turns out that Green Performance Appraisal has no effect on Sustainable Employee Performance, while Green Recruitment, Green Training, Green Compensation and Green Behavior have an effect on Sustainable Employee Performance among millennial managers in Indonesia. These findings have implications for companies for managing millennial managers in order to increase Sustainable Employee Performance.

Keywords: Green Human Resources management, Green behavior, Green Commitment, Sustainable Employee Performance.

1. INTRODUCTION

The development of the industrial world is increasingly massive and aggressive and has an impact on environmental damage due to the excessive use and exploitation of natural resources. To answer various challenges related to sustainability, companies are expected to pay attention to 3 aspects of sustainability, namely economic aspects, social aspects and environmental aspects in managing their business. In achieving sustainable organizational goals, it is necessary to have green conscious behavior among employees. Currently, the millennial

generation is quite dominating the world of work, which is known to have more varied behavior than the previous generation. They are more up to date on technology and have an out of the box mindset and great ideas. This innovative behavior from the millennial generation is what organizations really need to continue to develop and compete. Besides that, the role of the millennial generation in implementing green conscious behavior is very necessary for the sustainability of the organization. To find out the implementation of Employee Sustainable Performance, a pre-survey was conducted on 30 managers from several companies in Jakarta.

Table 1: Pre-survey Results of Sustainable Employee Performance

No	Question	Yes	No
1	I take the initiative to maintain environmentally conscious performance	12 (40%)	18 (60%)
2	I communicate effectively with colleagues and superiors	16 (53 %)	14 (47 %)
3	I always update my knowledge and skills to support my work while still paying attention to environmental conservation	15 (50 %)	15 (50 %)

Source: Data processing results

The survey results above prove that Sustainable Employee Performance is still not optimally implemented. Based on the results of interviews and reviews of previous research, there are several variables that are thought to influence Employee Green Behavior, namely Green Human Resources Management, Green Behavior & Green Commitment. To further clarify this, the researchers conducted a pre-survey with the results as follows:

Table 2: Pre-survey results of variables related to Sustainable Employee Performance

Question	Yes	No
Green Human Resources Management		
Employee assessment emphasizes environmental skills and competencies	11 (37 %)	19 (63 %)
Green Behavior		
I invite other employees to behave in a way that is beneficial to the environment	13 (43 %)	17 (57%)
Green Commitment		
I am proud of an environmentally friendly organization	14 (50 %)	16 (50%)

Source: Data processing results

The survey results above prove that Green Human Resources Management, Green Behavior & Green Commitment have not been implemented properly. Several previous research results prove that research results regarding the influence of green human resources on Sustainable Employee Performance are still inconsistent. Amjad's research (2021) proves that there is an effect of GHRM on Employee Performance. Research conducted by Zhang (2019) and Aboramadan (2020) states that GHRM has an effect on Green Behavior. Meanwhile, research conducted by Chaudhary (2019) proved that GHRM had no effect on Green Behavior. Research on the influence of Employee Green Behavior on employee performance conducted by Mayangsari et.al (2021) and Yong Jon (2019) states that there is an influence of Employee Green Behavior on employee performance. However, research by Muafi et.al (2022) states that there is no alignment between GHRM and Employee Green Behavior. Based on the gap phenomenon and gap research above, the aim of this research is to determine the influence of

Green Human Resource Management and Employee Green Behavior on Sustainable Employee Performance in the millennial generation.

2. THEORETICAL REVIEW

Green Human Resource Management

Green Human Resource Management (GHRM) is a company policy in managing human resources in a sustainable manner by involving environmental aspects to preserve nature in company management. GHRM is a development of Human Resource Management (HRM) which in Indonesia is known as human resource management, which is a policy and practice needed by someone who carries out aspects of people or recruiting, screening, training, and providing rewards and assessments (Sutawijaya et al, 2022).

Employee Green Behavior

Employee Green Behavior is employee behavior that is driven by ethical and pro-environmental behavior, whether mandatory due to regulations or voluntary, where this has become the norm in a company [Farooq et.al (2021), Xing et.al (2017)].

Green Commitment

Green commitment is the willingness of employees to prioritize environmental issues in the workplace [Raineri, 2016].

Sustainable Employee Performance

Sustainable Employee Performance refers to employees' contributions to their own sustainable development and projects and sustainable organizational development, and is divided into sustainable performance tasks and relationships with sustainable performance [Jiang et.al, 2017].

Based on the theory and previous research, the hypothesis in this study is:

- H1: Green Recruitment has a positive & significant effect on Green Behavior
- H2: Green Training has a significant effect on Green Behavior
- H3: Green Performance Appraisal has a significant effect on Green Behavior
- H4: Green Compensation has a significant effect on Green Behavior
- H5: Green Recruitment has a significant effect on Sustainable Employee Performance
- H6: Green Training has a significant effect on Sustainable Employee Performance
- H7: Green Performance Appraisal has a significant effect on Sustainable Employee Performance
- H8: Green Compensation has a significant effect on Sustainable Performance Employees
- H9: Green Behavior has a significant effect on Sustainable Employee Performance
- H10: Green Commitment moderates the effect of Green Behavior on Sustainable Employee Performance

Research Method

The type of research used is quantitative research with survey methods. The research sample used was 150 millennial generation managers. Data collection used a questionnaire with a Likert scale of 1-5. Data analysis using SEM PLS.

3. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Measurement Model Testing (Outer Model)

Validity test

1. Convergent Validity and AVE

In this study, the validity criteria were based on a reflexive indicator model which was measured by convergent validity, and AVE and discriminant validity. The indicator is said to meet convergent validity if the loading factor value is > 0.7 and the AVE value is > 0.5

Table 3: Convergent Validity and AVE values

Variable	Indicator	Outer Loadings	Information	AVE	
Green Recruitment (X1)	X1.1	0.878	Valid	0.807	Valid
	X1.2	0.919	Valid		
Green Training (X2)	X2.1	0.819	Valid	0.666	Valid
	X2.2	0.768	Valid		
	X2.3	0.858	Valid		
Green Performance Appraisal (X3)	X3.1	0.921	Valid	0.837	Valid
	X3.2	0.908	Valid		
Green Compensation (X4)	X4.1	0.907	Valid	0.772	Valid
	X4.2	0.829	Valid		
Green Behavior (Y1)	Y1.1	0.836	Valid	0.595	Valid
	Y1.2	0.815	Valid		
	Y1.3	0.782	Valid		
	Y1.4	0.803	Valid		
	Y1.5	0.746	Valid		
	Y1.6	0.706	Valid		
	Y1.7	0.752	Valid		
	Y1.8	0.731	Valid		
Sustainable Employee Performance (Y2)	Y2.1	0.756	Valid	0.605	Valid
	Y2.2	0.842	Valid		
	Y2.3	0.798	Valid		
	Y2.4	0.777	Valid		
	Y2.5	0.709	Valid		
	Y2.6	0.762	Valid		
Green Commitment (Z)	Z1	0.796	Valid	0.623	Valid
	Z2	0.778	Valid		
	Z3	0.836	Valid		
	Z4	0.814	Valid		
	Z5	0.753	Valid		
	Z6	0.755	Valid		

Source: Analysis results using SmartPLS 3

2. Discriminant Validity

The next validity test is the Discriminant Validity test. This test is based on the cross loading value. Cross loading factor to find out whether the latent variable has adequate discriminant, namely by comparing the correlation of indicators with the latent variable, it must be greater than the correlation between indicators and other latent variables (Imam Ghozali, 2015).

Table 4: Cross Loading Values

	Green Recruitment (X1)	Green Training (X2)	Green Performance Appraisal (X3)	Green Compensation (X4)	Green Behaviour (Y1)	Sustainable Employee Performance (Y2)	Green Commitment (Z)	Moderating Effect
Moderating Effect	0.181	0.136	0.143	0.149	-0.225	0.252	0.115	1.000
X1.1	0.878	0.491	0.540	0.550	0.364	0.516	0.548	0.224
X1.2	0.919	0.589	0.561	0.568	0.491	0.586	0.689	0.113
X2.1	0.554	0.819	0.600	0.662	0.473	0.448	0.585	-0.014
X2.2	0.364	0.768	0.279	0.406	0.375	0.535	0.490	0.109
X2.3	0.559	0.858	0.647	0.664	0.492	0.493	0.580	0.230
X3.1	0.588	0.575	0.921	0.648	0.471	0.443	0.555	0.173
X3.2	0.530	0.572	0.908	0.683	0.477	0.363	0.551	0.085
X4.1	0.597	0.650	0.730	0.907	0.542	0.485	0.581	0.213
X4.2	0.486	0.594	0.528	0.849	0.456	0.360	0.599	0.029
Y1.1	0.426	0.517	0.461	0.543	0.829	0.464	0.531	-0.240
Y1.2	0.354	0.446	0.460	0.468	0.815	0.438	0.475	-0.242
Y1.3	0.296	0.393	0.370	0.424	0.782	0.398	0.531	-0.260
Y1.4	0.444	0.374	0.445	0.438	0.803	0.482	0.527	-0.166
Y1.5	0.352	0.396	0.315	0.456	0.746	0.370	0.428	-0.225
Y1.6	0.314	0.365	0.288	0.368	0.706	0.468	0.426	-0.146
Y1.7	0.405	0.474	0.400	0.414	0.752	0.504	0.496	-0.109
Y1.8	0.359	0.401	0.427	0.404	0.731	0.477	0.530	-0.009
Y2.1	0.446	0.441	0.324	0.362	0.441	0.756	0.594	0.089
Y2.2	0.476	0.565	0.331	0.442	0.561	0.842	0.612	0.235
Y2.3	0.471	0.421	0.260	0.352	0.456	0.798	0.596	0.253
Y2.4	0.535	0.402	0.360	0.335	0.428	0.777	0.564	0.264
Y2.5	0.474	0.452	0.497	0.422	0.427	0.709	0.593	0.235
Y2.6	0.435	0.438	0.339	0.304	0.337	0.762	0.538	0.229
Y2.7	0.513	0.549	0.313	0.426	0.517	0.796	0.592	0.078
Z1	0.558	0.615	0.457	0.605	0.568	0.625	0.796	0.026
Z2	0.590	0.572	0.528	0.527	0.552	0.552	0.778	0.138
Z3	0.564	0.467	0.449	0.513	0.552	0.741	0.836	0.156
Z4	0.537	0.489	0.485	0.495	0.478	0.524	0.814	0.107
Z5	0.529	0.511	0.518	0.494	0.445	0.512	0.753	0.064
Z6	0.513	0.571	0.450	0.531	0.420	0.551	0.755	0.039

Source: Analysis results using SmartPLS 3

Discriminant Validity Test with Fornell-Lecker

The Fornell-Larcker Criterion method is a measurement method that suggests comparing the square root value of the Average Variance Extracted (AVE) of each latent variable with the correlation between other latent variables in the model. If the AVE square root value of each variable is greater than the correlation value between the variables and the other variables in the model, then the model is said to have good discriminant validity.

Table 5: Fornell-Larcker Criterion Values

	Green Recruitment (X1)	Green Training (X2)	Green Performance Appraisal (X3)	Green Compensation (X4)	Green Behaviour (Y1)	Sustainable Employee Performance (Y2)	Green Commitment (Z)	Moderating Effect
Green Recruitment (X1)	0.899		0.613	0.622	0.482		0.694	
Green Training (X2)	0.605	0.816	0.627	0.710	0.548		0.677	
Green Performance Appraisal (X3)			0.915	0.727	0.518		0.605	
Green Compensation (X4)				0.878	0.572		0.668	
Green Behaviour (Y1)					0.772			
Sustainable Employee Performance (Y2)	0.615	0.603	0.442	0.488	0.586	0.778	0.751	0.252
Green Commitment (Z)					0.641		0.789	
Moderating Effect	0.181	0.136	0.143	0.149	-0.225		0.115	1.000

Source: Analysis results using SmartPLS 3

Reliability Test

Construct reliability is measured by Composite Reliability and Cronbach's Alpha. A construct is said to be reliable if it has a Composite Reliability value > 0.7 and Cronbach's Alpha > 0.6 (Imam Ghozali, 2015).

Table 6: Cronbach's Alpha & Composite Reliability Values

	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability	Result
Green Recruitment (X1)	0.764	0.893	Reliabel
Green Training (X2)	0.748	0.857	Reliabel
Green Performance Appraisal (X3)	0.805	0.911	Reliabel
Green Compensation (X4)	0.707	0.871	Reliabel
Green Behaviour (Y1)	0.902	0.921	Reliabel
Sustainable Employee Performance (Y2)	0.891	0.915	Reliabel
Green Commitment (Z)	0.879	0.908	Reliabel
Moderating Effect	1.000	1.000	Reliabel

Source: Analysis results using SmartPLS 3

Measurement Model Testing (Outer Model)

This model is a specification of the relationship between latent variables, or it can also be called inner relations.

Figure 1: Inner Model with SmartPLS 3

Source: Processed from primary data using SmartPLS

At this testing stage, it is explained to assess the structural model with PLS, starting with looking at the R-squares value.

Test the Coefficient of Determination / R Square

R-squares for each endogenous latent variable as the predictive power of the structural model. The R-square value can be used to explain the influence of certain exogenous latent variables on whether endogenous latent variables have a substantive influence. R-squares values of 0.75, 0.50 and 0.25 can be concluded that the model is strong, moderate and weak. Apart from seeing the magnitude of the R-Squares value. The following are the results of the R-Squares values which can be seen in the table below:

Table 7: R-Square Value

Construct	R Square	R Square Adjusted
Green Behavior (Y1)	0.386	0.369
Sustainable Employee Performance (Y2)	0.683	0.667

Source: Analysis results using SmartPLS 3

Based on the data in Table 7, the relationship between variables based on the R Square value can be explained that the Green Behavior (Y1) variable is 0.386, this shows that 38.6% of the Green Behavior (Y1) variable is influenced by the Green Recruitment (X1), Green variables. Knowledge Management (X2), Green Performance Appraisal (X3) and Green Compensation (X4) simultaneously, while the remaining 61.4% is influenced by other variables outside those studied. The relationship between variables in Sustainable Employee Performance (Y2) is 0.683, meaning that 68.3% is influenced by the variables Green Recruitment (X1), Green Knowledge Management (X2), Green Performance Appraisal (X3) and Green Compensation (X4) simultaneously, while the remaining 31.7% is influenced by other variables beyond those studied.

Predictive Relevance Test (Q²)

To assess predictive relevance, use Cross validated redundancy (Q²) or Q-square test. Q² value > 0 indicates that the model has accurate predictive relevance for certain variables, while a Q² value < 0 indicates that the model lacks predictive relevance. Predictive relevance values of 0.02, 0.15, and 0.35 indicate that the research model is weak, moderate, and strong (Ghozali & Latan, 2021). The Cross-validated Redundancy (Q²) value is obtained through the Blindfolding procedure in SmartPLS v.3.2.9. The Q² value can be used to measure the observation values produced by the model and also to estimate parameters.

Q² value can be calculated by the following formula:

$$\begin{aligned}
 Q^2 &= 1 - ((1-R^2)(1-R^2).....(1-Rx^2)) \\
 &= 1 - (1-0.386^2) (1-0.683^2) \\
 &= 1 - (1-0.149^2) (1-0.466^2) \\
 &= 0.546
 \end{aligned}$$

Based on the calculation results above, it can be seen that the Q2 value > 0, so the model has a predictive relevance value, which means that the observed values generated by the model and

parameter estimates are good/relevant.

Value of Goodness of Fit Index (GoF)

Goodness of Fit Index (GoF) is calculated manually from the square root of the average communality index and average R-squares as follows:

$$\text{GoF} = \sqrt{\text{AVE} \times R^2}$$

$$\text{GoF} = \sqrt{0.738 \times 0.535}$$

$$\text{GoF} = \sqrt{0.395}$$

$$\text{GoF} = 0.628$$

Information:

The AVE value is obtained from the average AVE value of the research variables

as follows: $\text{AVE} = (0.807 + 0.666 + 0.837 + 0.772 + 0.595 + 0.605 + 0.623 + 1.00)/8 = 0.738$

The R square value (R²) is obtained from the average R square value of the dependent variable of the study as follows: $\text{R square (R}^2) = (0.386 + 0.683)/2 = 0.535$

The Goodness of Fit Index (GoF) calculation results show a value of 0.628.

Ghozali and Latan (2021) state that the value of the Goodness of Fit Index (GoF) is classified as: small = 0.1, medium = 0.25 and large = 0.36. The results of the calculation of the Goodness of Fit Index (GoF) in this study is 0.628 so it can be concluded that the combined performance of the measurement model (outer model) and the structural model (inner model) as a whole is good because the value of the Goodness of Fit Index (GoF) is more than 0.36 (large category GoF scale).

Effect Size Test (f square)

The f square test (f²) aims to assess the magnitude of the influence between variables. The f² value = 0.02 as small, 0.15 as medium, and 0.35 as large (Ghozali & Latan, 2021).

Table 8: Value of f square (f²)

Variable	f-square	Result
Green Recruitment (X1) ---> Green Behaviour (Y1)	0.011	Small
Green Recruitment (X1) ---> Sustainable Employee Performance (Y2)	0.039	Intermediate
Green Training (X2) ---> Green Behaviour (Y1)	0.035	Intermediate
Green Training (X2) ---> Sustainable Employee Performance (Y2)	0.041	Intermediate
Green Performance Appraisal (X3) ---> Green Behaviour (Y1)	0.011	Small
Green Performance Appraisal (X3) ---> Sustainable Employee Performance (Y2)	0.022	Intermediate
Green Compensation (X4) ---> Green Behaviour (Y1)	0.037	Intermediate
Green Compensation (X4) ---> Sustainable Employee Performance (Y2)	0.045	Intermediate
Green Behaviour (Y1) ---> Sustainable Employee Performance (Y2)	0.166	Intermediate
Green Commitment (Z) ---> Sustainable Employee Performance (Y2)	0.241	Intermediate
Moderating Effect ---> Sustainable Employee Performance (Y2)	0.178	Intermediate

Hypothesis testing

The next stage is testing the hypothesis between constructs which is carried out by the bootstrap resampling method. Calculation of hypothesis testing using smartPLS 3.3.3 can be seen from the path coefficient value, besides that it can be seen whether or not there is an influence between exogenous variables on endogenous variables based on the P-value. As for knowing the level of significance measured based on t-statistics, as well as to know the strength of the influence of exogenous variables on endogenous variables can be known based on the values contained in the original sample. The results of testing the hypothesis using smartPLS 3 software can be seen in the following table.

Table 9: Hypothesis Testing for Direct Effects

	Original Sample (O)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values	Result
Green Behaviour (Y1) -> Sustainable Employee Performance (Y2)	0.348	0.074	4.702	0.000	Positive and significant influence
Green Commitment (Z) -> Sustainable Employee Performance (Y2)	0.476	0.075	6.333	0.000	Positive and significant influence
Green Compensation (X4) -> Green Behaviour (Y1)	0.252	0.117	2.161	0.031	Positive and significant influence
Green Compensation (X4) -> Sustainable Employee Performance (Y2)	-0.208	0.099	2.096	0.037	Positive and significant influence
Green Performance Appraisal (X3) -> Green Behaviour (Y1)	0.126	0.115	1.088	0.277	Has no effect and is not significant
Green Performance Appraisal (X3) -> Sustainable Employee Performance (Y2)	-0.129	0.102	1.267	0.206	Has no effect and is not significant
Green Recruitment (X1) -> Green Behaviour (Y1)	0.113	0.093	1.221	0.223	Has no effect and is not significant
Green Recruitment (X1) -> Sustainable Employee Performance (Y2)	0.168	0.083	2.027	0.043	Positive and significant influence
Green Training (X2) -> Green Behaviour (Y1)	0.222	0.100	2.226	0.026	Positive and significant influence
Green Training (X2) -> Sustainable Employee Performance (Y2)	0.180	0.090	2.011	0.045	Positive and significant influence
Moderating Effect 1 -> Sustainable Employee Performance (Y2)	0.263	0.037	7.049	0.000	Positive and significant influence

Source: Analysis results using SmartPLS 3

Based on table 9 it is known that H2, H4, H5, H6, H8, H9 and H10 in this study were declared accepted because the t statistic value was greater than the t table value and the p value was less than 0.05. Whereas H1, H3 and H7 were declared rejected because the t statistic value was smaller than the t table value and the p value was greater than 0.05.

Discussion

Green Recruitment has no effect on Green Behavior. In implementing green recruitment, companies still do not include criteria for prospective employees who pay attention to the environment in the recruitment process, so this causes the implementation of Green recruitment to not be optimal. The results of this research support research conducted by Chaudhary (2019) which states that Green Human Resources Management has no effect on Employee Green Behavior. Green Training influences Green Behavior. The company has conducted training on the environment so that this will increase the Green behavior of employees including managers. Results This research is supported by the results of research conducted by Zibarras and Coan (2015) which proves GHRM practices are more effective than others in encouraging pro-environmental behavior. Green Performance Appraisal has no effect on Green Behavior. In several companies studied, it turns out that the company does not yet have green performance indicators in its performance management system, so this will affect the Green Behavior of managers. This research is different from research conducted by Afsar et.al (2018) which proves that Green HRM practices positively influence employees' pro-environmental behavior.

Green Compensation influences Green Green Behavior. One of the implementations of Green Competition is that several companies have provided recognition-based awards to encourage employee participation in environmental management. The results of this research are supported by previous research conducted by Zhang (2019) and Aboramadan (2020) stating that GHRM has an effect on Green Behavior. Green Recruitment has an influence on Sustainable Employee Performance. Good implementation related to Green Recruitment will increase Sustainable Employee Performance. In its implementation, companies began to prefer to employ employees who had environmental awareness. The results of this study support research conducted by research is the research conducted by Deepak (2015) and Marco et.al (2015) which proves that the practice of Green Human Resources Management has practically produced positive results on Green Performance.

Green Training has an effect on Sustainable Employee Performance. Implementation of good Green Training will increase Sustainable Employee Performance. In addition to conducting various trainings, both hard skills and soft skills related to competence in jobs that focus on being environmentally friendly, the company also conducts training evaluations. Research that supports the results of this study is research conducted by Jie Shen (2016) that the GHRM practice adopted by the organization to improve the Green Performance of employees in the workplace. Green Performance Appraisal has no effect on Sustainable Employee Performance. Implementation of Green Performance Appraisal in companies, it turns out that many of the companies studied do not have an integrated system related to Green Performance Appraisal. The results of this study contradict the results of research conducted by Elsayy (2022) which proves a significant relationship between the Sustainable components of HRM and Sustainable

Employee Performance. Green Compensation influences Sustainable Employee Performance. Good implementation of Green Compensation will lead to an increase in Employee Sustainable Performance. The results of this study are supported by research conducted by Hiba research (2016) which states that empirical assessment and measurement of the impact of GHRM practices in manufacturing organizations have an influence on Green Performance in the Palestinian context.

Green Behavior influences Sustainable Employee Performance. Good implementation related to Green Behavior will affect Sustainable Employee Performance. Managers have an attitude of accepting and learning from feedback regarding the implementation of Green Human Resources Management and Employee Green Behavior so that this will improve sustainable employee performance in the company. The results of this research support the results of research conducted by Mayangsari et.al (2021) which stated that Employee Green Behavior has a positive and significant effect on Environmental Performance, apart from that Employee Green behavior as an intervening Green HRM also has an effect on Environmental Performance. The results are also in line with Kim's research. et al (2019) proved that employees' environmentally friendly behavior affects hotel environmental performance. Other research conducted by Andersson (2013) also states that there is an influence of Green Behavior carried out by individual employees and work groups related to Green Performance.

Green Commitment moderates the effect of Green Behavior on Sustainable Employee Performance. With the Green Commitment, the influence of Green Behavior on Sustainable Employee Performance will be even greater. Employees feel proud of an environmentally friendly organization. This pride further increases employee engagement with the company so that this will increase Sustainable Employee Performance.

4. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Conclusion

The results of this study prove that Green Training and Green Compensation have an effect on Green Behavior while Green Recruitment and Green Performance Appraisal have no effect on Green Behavior. Green Performance Appraisal apparently has no effect on Sustainable Employee Performance while Green Recruitment, Green Training, Green Compensation and Green Behavior have an effect on Sustainable Employee Performance for millennial managers in Indonesia. As expected, it turns out that Green Commitment moderates the effect of Green Behavior on Sustainable Employee Performance.

Suggestion

The results of this research prove that not all dimensions of Green Human Resources Management influence Green Behavior in millennial generation managers in Indonesia. Future researchers are expected to enrich literature related to Green Human Resources Management, Employee Green Behavior, Green Commitment & Sustainable Employee Performance. Apart from that, it is also hoped to examine other variables that are thought to influence Sustainable Employee Performance such as Green Leadership and Green Culture.

Apart from that, our findings also provide managerial implications, to further improve Sustainable Employee Performance, there are several things that are recommended for companies. First, companies are expected to include environmental criteria in the recruitment process and prefer employee candidates who have environmental awareness. Second, companies are expected to hold environmental training and provide online training materials. Third, companies are expected to have green performance indicators in their performance management assessment system and carry out performance evaluations related to the environment. Fourth, companies are expected to provide recognition-based awards to encourage employee participation in environmental management and provide financial incentives for employees who promote/implement environmentally friendly behavior. Fifth, managers must be aware of keeping the environment clean and saving energy (example: turning off lights and computers when not in use). Sixth, managers must have an attitude of accepting and learning from feedback. With Green Human Resources Management, millennial generation managers are expected to feel emotionally connected to environmentally friendly organizations so that it will increase Sustainable Employee Performance.

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